

DEVELOPMENT AND GROWTH OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the world , the young people are paid great attention to the education , their relevant professions, the reform of the education system and the training of national personnel to the level of modern requirements. In our republic, one of the main directions of the society's needs is the organization and updating of content in primary school in accordance with modern requirements, connection of continuing education with science and industry, further improvement of the system of higher education institutions in the field of pedagogy, strengthening methodological training of competitive teachers, that article , some issues of improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education will be considered.

Key words: Education, upbringing. the process of pedagogy , teacher, thinker, method, activity, the system of education , content and form.

"The continuation of the path of further development of the system of continuing education, increasing access to quality educational services, training of highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market"¹, as well as sharply developing the quality of general secondary education; Extensive work is being done to train specialists in meeting the needs of employers and to improve the quality and efficiency of their activities in the higher education system. In our country, the methodological training of future primary school teachers in a constantly changing situation , learning advanced foreign experience, the improvement of technology to increase the methodological training of teachers in primary education, didactic methods, pedagogical conditions, content and structure, criteria and levels of formation, form , method, vocations, model, increasing the efficiency of teaching quality, as well as the development of theoretical and practical factors to improve the preparation of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education. In today, One of the main requirements is to enrich the training, knowledge and experience of future teachers, such as fully mature, knowledgeable and creative youth in today's period of renewal and spiritual growth. Therefore, the importance and contribution of the science of education is incomparable.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan in improving the system of continuing education , developing the quality and effectiveness of education, methodological training of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education is important in terms of level, potential and importance as a pedagogical issues.

In the system of primary education , the education of students play a special role in the development of the system of educational work and the creation of the necessary conditions for students to operate in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Today, the main goal of the methodological training of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education is to form the younger generation as fully developed, well-rounded people necessary for the development of our society. An ideal person embodies spiritual and physical maturity. For the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education, firstly , folklore, folk tales, stories, legends, the spiritual heritage of our ancestors and historical books play a key role. In addition, the heritage

¹ Towards sharply development and renewal based on action strategy//T.: "G.Gulom", -2017.-70P.

of Eastern thinkers, poems and ghazals, fictions of art serve as a program. Based on the socio-political, philosophical and educational views of scholars such as Ahmad Yassavi, Bahovuddin Naqshbandi, Al-Bukhari, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abulqasim Firdavsi, Amur Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babir the development of the learning process requires further excellence.

Methodological training of future primary school teachers to teach the subject of education is the basis of the educational process, a pedagogical problem that requires constant attention, does not lose relevance.

It can be seen that different methods of teaching have been applied in practice when studying the history of the development of educational methods in Central Asia. In particular, in his work "Tadbir al-ma'nozil" of Abu Ali ibn Sina says that young children should be brought up in a certain order from birth to adulthood. He prefers to teach children in groups rather than individually, and writes about the advantages of this method: "Students feel a thirst for knowledge during reading and upbringing. When students are together, they always speak to each other and thus, improve their upbringing and speech."

According to Yan Amos Komenski The problems of educating a highly spiritual person have a special place, who claimed that the leading role of the sensory organs in the cognitive system, describing the empirical, scientific and practical stages in the development of cognitive processes, the main sources of cognition which notion and concept [61].

KD Ushinsky was one of the first to create the mechanism of development of educational activity, which consists in the development of the qualities of upbringing, idea and willpower. He emphasizes the need to cultivate confidence and determination in the ideas that are formed in the process of developing students' educational qualities [112].

In pedagogical works of Abdulla Avloni, "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" is one of great importance in the field of learning the improvement of pedagogical ideas in the early XX century. The novel of "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" is a moral and educational work. The novel is about a science that "calls people to goodness and turns them away from evil." From this point of view, that novel is a kind of educational work in the form of Yusuf Khas Hajib's "Qutadg'u bilig", Nasir Khisrav's "Saodatnoma", Sa'di's "Gulistan" and "Boston", Jomi's "Bahoriston", Navoi's "Mahbub ul-kulub", Ahmad Donish's "Advice to children."

Abdulla Avloni said that thinking about the role of child rearing as a teacher, "If a person grows up immoral, uneducated and immoral in his youth, to expect good from such people is like reaching out to the stars from the ground." According to him, the social environment, family conditions and the people around the child play an important role in the formation of moral qualities in children.

For the first time in the history of Uzbek pedagogy, Abdulla Avloni described that

"Pedagogy is the subject of child rearing". Naturally, such a description indicates that Avloni was well versed in the science of pedagogy. Abdulla Avloni divides into the upbringing of children into the following 4 sections: 1. "The age of upbringing." 2. "Physical training". 3. "Education of thought." 4. Thinks about "moral education" and its importance. The section "Time of upbringing" claims the need to educate from an early age, and everyone should be involved in this work: parents, teachers, government and others. "Education is for us a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster,"- says Abdulla Avloni. Education is not a private issue, it is a national, social affair. The author describes that the development of any nation, the strength of states based on many ways on the upbringing of generations. The

upbringing begins from the birth of the offspring and continues until the end of life. It consists of several stages: home, kindergarten, school and community education.

Avloni understands the scope of upbringing in a broad sense. It does not limit it to morality alone. She says she should take care of the child's health first. According to Avloni, it is necessary to cultivate the body in order to have a sound mind, good morals, knowledge and enlightenment.

“Keeping the body healthy and strong is the one most important thing for human . Because in order to read, to teach, to learn and to understand, a person needs a strong, disease-free body. ”

While Abdulla Avloni addresses parents on the issue of physical education in the healthy upbringing of the child, he pays special attention to the activities of teachers in the mental upbringing of the child.

In the researches of pedagogical scientists of the Republic S.Nishonova, M.Kuronov the concepts of upbringing of the harmoniously developed generation and formation of the harmoniously developed person are created on the basis of formation of spiritual and moral consciousness of the student [76, 65].

At the same time, the psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature identifies the tasks aimed at organizing the educational work of students, but they are not sufficiently covered in the education system, practical guidelines are not developed. The pedagogical conditions necessary for the organization of educational work of students in the classroom are not defined.

It is a very necessary and sacred task for students to develop and cultivate pedagogical qualities on a regular basis. Therefore, it is a "sacred duty of teachers, which is based on their attention and conscience ... Because the power, beauty, breadth of thought depends on the teacher's upbringing "1.

Today's requirement is to upbringing young people in the spirit of faith, devotion to the national idea, love for each other, respect for their motherland, nation, religion, language, history, culture and traditions. Thus, by educating citizens on the basis of new thinking, it is possible to form and develop a behavior that is in line with the vital human principles of the national idea and ideology, universal values, that is, to establish a culture of kindness in society.

"The Year of Youth Support and Health Promotion" has been declared in 2021 . It is important that a significant part of the work carried out this year will be directed at youth and their education. The role of state policy in the spiritual and educational improvement of our youth is incomparable. In our President's speech claimed the importance of supporting young people. “In general, the decisive role in the development of any society is played by the healthy and harmonious development of the younger generation, on which the future of this society depends. So, we consider our enthusiastic, enterprising, well-developed young people with modern knowledge and skills as our basis for expanding and further enhancing the effectiveness of our reforms, ”- he said. The President emphasized the need to create an environment and conditions for the upbringing of new Khorezmi, Beruni, Ibn Sino, Ulugbek, Navoi and Babur in order to form the foundation of a new Renaissance in our country.

“Our top priority should be to set ambitious goals and create competent youth to achieve them. Only then will our children become a real force that will realize the age-old dreams of our people, ”they said. He expressed satisfaction with the bold ideas and initiatives expressed by youth during the meetings in Kashkadarya, Khorezm and Chilanzar regions of Tashkent.

“Especially at the recent Youth Forum, seeing the passionate eyes of our youth, their passion for knowledge, I was very empowered. And I am once again convinced that they are the brave and determined youth that Ibn Sina said,

"I am confident that together with learned youth, with strong creative potential, we will build a new Uzbekistan," he said.

In our country, the dedication of each year to a specific social issue also had a deep symbolic meaning. Thus, the expected result cannot be achieved without a loving approach to everything, the highest feeling in the human heart. Therefore, it is important to treat the national idea and ideology with sincerity, to study its historical, philosophical, religious and moral roots, to inculcate the heritage of our ancestors in the minds of our youth at every stage of education.

In turn, the special tasks set over the years are neither a one-time action nor a ‘complex of actions’, but a worldview and character, an integral part of the inner spirituality of man, a sign of the culture of society.

Based on the above considerations, we think it is necessary to clarify the role of education in the formation of national ideas and ideologies.

In our opinion, setting a priority every year is the main goal of the idea of national independence from the humanitarian point of view. Therefore, in the process of education, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the tasks arising from the same specific goal.

It is well known that upbringing is used in a broad and narrow sense and is practiced in social life. In a broad sense, upbringing is a special process that transmits socio-cultural experiences from generation to generation with a clear purpose and creates the conditions for the development of the individual.

In the narrow sense, the education of spiritual culture means the process of jointly focused goal-oriented activities of adults in adapting young people to the complex situations of social life, that is, the process of creating the necessary conditions for the development of a mature person.

These processes are inextricably connected. For that reason, it is necessary to develop and implement effective organizational and pedagogical methods and tools for the formation of the spiritual culture of youth. The various forms and means of the national education system must be based on the national cultural and historical traditions, customs and universal values of our people, which ensure the realization of the national idea, the formation of a harmoniously developed generation. Education has always been the most important task in front of humanity. It is also organized based on people’s current experiences, achievements, customs and traditions. So, we have a lot of many traditions, eternal traditions of education. Even today, they are widely used in educating youth. Moreover, as the First President I.A. Karimov said that "We must always remember that the future of our country depends on how our young generation is brought up, what spiritual qualities they grow up, how active our children are in life, what lofty goals they serve."² There is no doubt that the increase in the volume of knowledge and information will lead to the expansion of people's worldview and the rise of their spirituality. At the same time, the formation of the ability to distinguish true, objective and useful information from incessant and unsystematic incoming messages is becoming a very important task.

Each country is interested in providing its population, especially youth with a thirst for knowledge and innovation, with scientific knowledge, enlightenment and spiritual nourishment.

² Journal of Communication, 1999 y №4.21-p

In Uzbekistan, a principled information policy aimed at meeting the intellectual needs of the younger generation, preserving cultural, spiritual and moral values has been formed and is being implemented.

On reforming the education system in the country the work being done is aimed at the same goal. This issue is ideologically consistent with the principles of the Law on Education. The importance of the study of our national educational heritage is theoretically side. In particular, the principles of the national model of continuing education, in essence, mean that education is carried out in harmony with the national-enlightenment, national history, folk traditions, our national heritage. According to the national model of education in general, the modernization of the education system naturally shows the need to study our national heritage and bring it into the consumption of pedagogical thinking.

A true person will have the potential to self-educate. He renounces habits that are useless and harmful to himself and the nation. He relises the interests of the nation as his own interests as a condition for achieving the interests of the nation. He feels his role in reconciling the day of the nation, in lightening its burden. That is why, he rises above his own personal shell and works more, more effectively, than others, for the benefit of the nation, for the perfection of himself through the welfare of the nation. The national idea, believes in the goal, connects it. In a student, these qualities do not appear all at once. They are brought up, firstly, by encouraging the educational environment between parents in the family, relatives outside the family, neighbors, and then in higher education - by acquiring ideological knowledge. Therefore, this process should be considered as one of the priorities of social pedagogy.

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